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AGABABYAN Irina Rubenovna
t.f.n., dotsent**KOBILOVA Nigina Akmalovna**
Samarqand Davlat Tibbiyot Universiteti**CHANGES IN THE LEVEL OF C-REACTIVE PROTEIN IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY INTERVENTION WHILE TAKING COLCHICINE**

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ANNOTATION

Purpose: To study the effect of colchicine on the level of C-reactive protein in patients undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI).

Materials and methods: We conducted an analysis with coronary heart disease, who underwent myocardial infarction, underwent PCI from August 1 to November 1, 2022 according to the Samarkand regional regional branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Cardiology. A total of 52 patients were analyzed, who underwent interventional intervention (PCI), stenting of the coronary arteries with radial access.

Conclusion: The use of colchicine at a dose of 0.5 mg per day for 3 months after PCI significantly reduced the level of C-reactive protein, and in the group without colchicine, CRP remained practically at the same positions.

Keywords: Colchicine, C-reactive protein, percutaneous coronary admixture (PCI), atherosclerosis, CAD.

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KOLXITSINNI QABUL QILISH PAYTIDA TERI ORQALI KORONAR ARALASHUVNI BOSH DAN KECHIRAYOTGAN BEMORLARDA C-REAKTIV OQSIL DARAJASINING O'ZGARISHI**ANNOTATSIYA**

Maqsad: Perkutan koronar intervensiya (PCI) o'tkazilayotgan bemorlarda kolxitsinning C-reaktiv oqsil darajasiga ta'sirini o'rganish.

Materiallar va metodlar: Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan kardiologiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazi Samarqand viloyati hududiy filiali ma'lumotlariga ko'ra 2022-yil 1-avgustdan 1-noyabrga qadar yurak ishemik kasalligi, miokard infarkti bo'lgan, PCI tekshiruvdan o'tganlar bilan tahlil o'tkazdik. Jami 52 bemor tahlil qilindi, ular intervension aralashuv (PCI), radial kirish bilan koronar arteriyalarni stentlashdan o'tkazildi.

Xulosa: PCI dan keyin 3 oy davomida kuniga 0,5 mg dozada kolxisinni qo'llash C-reaktiv oqsil darajasini sezilarli darajada pasaytirdi va kolxisinsiz guruhda CRP deyarli bir xil pozitsiyalarda qoldi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kolxitsin, C-reaktiv oqsil, teri orqali koronar aralashuv (TKA), ateroskleroz, yurak ishemik kasalligi.

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ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ УРОВНЯ С-РЕАКТИВНОГО БЕЛКА У БОЛЬНЫХ, ПЕРЕНЕСШИХ ЧРЕСКОЖНОЕ КОРОНАРНОЕ ВМЕШАТЕЛЬСТВО НА ФОНЕ ПРИЕМА КОЛХИЦИНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель: Изучить влияние колхицина на уровень С-реактивного белка у больных перенесших чрескожное коронарное вмешательство (ЧКВ).

Материалы и методы: Нами был проведен анализ с ишемической болезнью сердца, перенесших инфаркт миокарда, подвергшихся ЧКВ с 1 августа по 1 ноябрь 2022 по данным Самаркандского областного регионального филиала Республиканского специализированного научно-практического медицинского центра кардиологии. Всего было проанализировано 52 больных, которым было проведено интервенционное вмешательство (ЧКВ), стентирование коронарных артерий радиальным доступом.

Заключение: Применение колхицина в дозе 0.5мг в сутки в течение 3х месяцев после ЧКВ значительно снизило уровень С-реактивного белка, а в группе без колхицина практически СРБ остался на тех же позициях.

Ключевые слова: Колхицин, С-реактивный белок, чрескожное коронарное вмешательство (ЧКВ), атеросклероз, ИБС.

Kirish

Mumkin bo'lgan turmush tarzi o'zgarishiga va xavf omillarini kamaytirishga qaramay, surunkali koronar kasalligi bo'lgan bemorlarda o'tkir yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfi yuqori bo'lib qolmoqda. Butun dunyoda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari yigirma yil oldin o'limning asosiy sababi bo'lib, hozirgi vaqtda bemorlar o'z sog'lig'i haqida ko'proq ma'lumotga ega bo'lishlariga qaramay, ko'plab turli xil dori-darmonlar va turli xil aralashuvlar – qon- tomirni stentlash va aortokoronar shuntlash jarrohligi ularning umrini uzaytirishi mumkin[12,13]. Tekshiruvning doimiy yaxshilanishiga qaramay va davolash usullari, koronar arteriya kasalliklaridan o'lim darajasi yuqori bo'lib qolmoqda, va shuning uchun yangi izlash va rivojlantirish koronar tomir kasalligi bilan og'rigan bemorlarni davolash usullari olib borilmoqda. [4]So'nggi yillarda koronar kasallikning rivojlanishida yallig'lanishning roli yaxshi ma'lum bo'ldi [3,5]. Yallig'lanishga qarshi terapiyaning CV natijalarini yaxshilash imkoniyatini birinchi bo'lib Niderlandiyada, ilgari miyokard infarkti bo'lgan bemorlarda Canakinumab yallig'lanishga qarshi tromboz (CANTOS) natijalarini o'rganishda [11] ta'kidlangan bo'lib, unda C-reaktiv oqsilning asosiy darajasini o'rgangan [10]. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, platsebo olganlarga qaraganda kanakinumab olganlar orasida yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining takrorlanish xavfi past bo'lgan. Kolxitsin - yallig'lanishga qarshi dori bo'lib, dastlab kuzgi krokuslardan (Colchicum kuzgi) olingan va qadimgi yunonlar va misrliklar tomonidan ishlatilgan. Kanakinumab tomonidan interleykin-1b ni tanlab ingibirlashdan farqli o'laroq, kolxitsin tubulin polimerizatsiyasini bloklaydi va leykotsitlar sezgirligini o'zgartirishni o'z ichiga olgan keng hujayrali ta'sirga ega.

Kolxitsinning yallig'lanishga qarshi ta'siri bir nechta mexanizmlar bilan, eng muhimi, yallig'lanishni to'xtatish bilan bog'liq [14]. Yallig'lanishlar blokadasi va kaspaza mexanizmi faolligining pasayishi bilan piroptoz (dasturlashtirilgan hujayra o'limi) va IL-1b va IL-18 sitokinlarini ishlab chiqarish kamayadi [13]. Natijada, turli xil qo'zg'atuvchilar bilan - ateroskleroz, giperurikemiya, virusli infeksiya, kolxitsin yallig'lanishga qarshi potentsialga ega va sitokin bo'ronini oldini olishga qodir [6,7]. Kolxitsinning yurak-qon tomir natijalarini o'rganishda (COLCOT) o'rganishga kirishdan oldin 30 kun ichida miyokard infarkti bo'lgan bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir o'limi, reanimatsiya qilingan yurak tuxtashi, miokard infarkti, insult yoki shoshilinch kasalxonaga yotqizishning umumiy yakuniy nuqtasi bo'lgan bemorlarning foizi. angina, ko'p tomirli koronar revaskulyarizatsiyaga bo'lgan talab kuniga bir marta 0,5 mg kolxitsin olganlar orasida platsebo guruhida bo'lgan bemorlarga qaraganda pastroq bo'lgan.[14]

Maqsad: Teri orqali koronar aralashuv (PCI) o'tkazilayotgan bemorlarda kolxitsinning C-reaktiv oqsil darajasiga ta'sirini o'rganish.

Materiallar va uslublar: Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan kardiologiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazi Samarqand viloyati hududiy filiali ma'lumotlariga asosan 2022-yil 1-avgustdan 1-noyabrgacha bo'lgan davrda PCI tekshiruvidan o'tgan bemorlarni tahlil qildik. Surunkali koronar yurak kasalligi bo'lgan miokard infarkti bo'lgan, radial kirish bilan intervension aralashuvni (PCI) o'tkazgan jami 52 nafar bemor tahlil qilindi. Erkaklar 76,92% (n=40), ayollar 23,1% (n=12). Bemorlar ko'r-ko'rona randomizatsiyalangan tadqiqot orqali ikki guruhga bo'lingan: birinchi guruh kolxitsin va asosiy dorilarni (b-blokerlar, kaltsiy kanallari blokerlari, nitratlar, antikoagulyantlar, antiplatelet agentlari, statinlar) qabul qilgan 27 bemordan iborat bo'lgan, ikkinchi guruh 25 kishidan iborat bo'lib, yuqoridagi barcha preparatlarni kolxitsinsiz olgan bemorlar. Dastlab, PCI dan oldin barcha bemorlar kardiolog tomonidan tekshirildi va umumiy va biokimyoviy qon testlari, EKG, ekokardiyografi, ko'krak qafasi rentgenogrammasi va koronar angiografiya buyurildi. O'rtacha yoshi: birinchi guruh 64,51±9,2 yil; ikkinchi guruh 62,48±8,0 yil.

Jadval 1

Dastlabki bosqichda bemorlarni o'rganish xususiyatlari

Xarakterli	Kolxitsin n=27	Platsebo n=25
Yosh - yil	64,51±9,2	62,48±8,1
Ayollar (%)	5(18,5)	7(28)
Hozirgi chekuvchi -%	14(51,8)	12(48)
Gipertonik kasallik - (%)	20(74)	18(72)
Qandli diabet - (%)	3(11,1)	2(8)
- qandli diabet uchun har qanday davolanishni olayotgan bemorlar	3(11,1)	2(8)
-insulinga qaram bo'lgan bemorlar, 2-toifa diabet	0	0
Atriyal fibrilatsiya tarixi - (%)	4(14,8)	3(12)
Podagra tarixi - (%)	2(7,4)	3(12)

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, tadqiqot guruhida ayollar erkaklarnikiga qaraganda ancha kam edi. Ikkinchi guruh uchun ham xuddi shunday edi. Komorbid patologiyasi bo'lgan ikkala guruhdagi bemorlarning ko'pchiligi gipertenziya bilan og'rigan (birinchi guruhdagi bemorlarning 74% va ikkinchi guruhdagi bemorlarning 72%). Ikkinchi turdagi qandli diabet birinchi guruhdagi bemorlarda 11,1% va ikkinchi guruhda 8%, bo'lmacha fibrilatsiya (doimiy shakl) birinchi guruhda 14,8% va ikkinchi guruhda 12% kuzatilgan. Ikkala guruhdagi barcha bemorlarda miokard revaskulyarizatsiyasi o'tkazildi: barcha stentlar to'liq revaskulyarizatsiya bilan dori-darmonli edi. Revaskulyarizatsiya jarayoni barcha bemorlarda asoratsiz yakunlandi.

Jadval 2

Miyokardiyal revaskulyarizatsiya qilingan bemorlar

	Kolxitsin n=27	Platsebo n=25
AKSH (Aorto-koronar shuntlash) %	11(11,1)	8(8)

PCI (stentlash) %	16(59,3)	17(48)
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Jadval 3

Miyokard revaskulyarizatsiyasidan keyin shifoxonada qo'llaniladigan dorilar.

	Kolxitsin n=27	Platsebo n=25
Asetilsalitsil kislotasi 75 mg, klopidoqrel 75 mg (%)	27 (100)	25 (100)
Ksarelto 10 mg (%)	3(11,1)	2(8)
Antiagregantlar yoki antikoagulyantlar yo'q	0	0
Rosuvastatin 20 mg (%)	24(88,9)	22(88)
Perindopril 4 mg (%)	15(55,6)	13(52)
Bisoprolol 5 mg (%)	23(85,2)	22(88)

Teri orqali koronar aralashuv jarayonidan so'ng barcha bemorlarga 3 oy davomida 75 mg atsetilsalitsil kislotasi va 75 mg klpedogrel shaklida ikki tomonlama antiagregant terapiyasi buyurildi. Bo'lmacha fibrilatsiyasi bo'lgan bemorlarga antikoagulyant rivaroksaban kuniga 15 mg dozada buyurilgan.

Kuniga 0,5 mg dozada kolxitsin birinchi guruhdagi bemorlar tomonidan 3 oy davomida qabul qilingan. Dastlab, har ikkala guruhda C-reaktiv oqsil darajasi yuqori bo'lgan : $57,92 \pm 9,67$ va $52,48 \pm 9,01$. Birinchi guruhda kolxitsinni uch oy qabul qilgandan so'ng C-reaktiv oqsil darajasi sezilarli darajada pasayib, o'rtacha $16,85 \pm 2,12$ mg/l ga teng bo'lgan bo'lsa, kolxitsin olmagan ikkinchi guruhda C-reaktiv oqsil ancha yuqoriligicha qoldi $46,6 \pm 9,14$ mg/l.

1-Rasm Kolxitsinni qabul qilish fonida C-reaktiv oqsil (mg/l) darajasining o'zgarishi

Natijalar. Ikkala guruhda ham miokard revaskulyarizatsiyasidan o'tgan barcha bemorlarda C-reaktiv oqsil miqdori dastlab birinchi guruhda o'rtacha $57,92 \pm 9,67$ mg / l ga ko'tarildi, ular kuniga 0,5 mg dozada asosiy terapiya fonida kolxitsinni qabul qildilar va ikkinchi guruhdagi faqat asosiy terapiyada bo'lgan bemorlarda C-reaktiv oqsil miqdori $52,48 \pm 9,01$ mg / l ko'tarilgan edi. 3 oydan so'ng, TKA dan keyin birinchi guruhdagi bemorlarda kolxitsinni qabul qilishda C-reaktiv oqsil sezilarli darajada kamaydi, ikkinchi guruhda ham C-reaktiv oqsil darajasi kamaydi, lekin sezilarli darajada emas.

Olingan natijalar myhokamasi. Bir qator tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, yurak etishmovchiligi bo'lgan va bo'lmachalar fibrilatsiya tufayli ablatsyon bo'lgan bemorlarda

kolxitsinning past dozalari yallig'lanish markyorlari darajasini shu jumladan yuqori sezgir C-reaktiv oqsil va interleykin-6 ni ishonchli tarzda kamaytirishi; ammo, faqat bitta tasodifiy tadqiqotda barqaror ishemik yurak kasalligi bo'lgan bemorlarda biokimyoviy ta'siri o'rganib chiqildi [8]. C-reaktiv oqsil, shuningdek, yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlar, aterosklerotik yurak kasalligi bo'lgan bemorlarda yallig'lanishni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. 3 oy davomida kuniga 0,5 mg dozada uzoq muddatli foydalanish bilan kolxisin C-reaktiv oqsil darajasini sezilarli darajada kamaytiradi ($57,92 \pm 9,67$ dan $16,85 \pm 2,12$ mg / l gacha). Tadqiqotlarimiz tugamadi. Bemorlar hozircha kolxisini qabul qilishda davom etmoqdalar.

Xulosa: Kolxisin LoDoCo (kuniga 0,5 mg dan past dozali kolxisin) preparatning yallig'lanishga qarshi va antilipidemik ta'siri bo'yicha tavsiyalarini yana bir bor tasdiqladi, u kolxitsinning barqaror yurak tomirlari kasalligi bilan og'riqan bemorlarga ta'sirini o'rgandi [9] va LoDoCo2 (Avstraliya va Gollandiyada o'tkazilgan tadqiqot), shuningdek, qabul qilinadigan xavfsizlik profili va arzonligi [1,2] tufayli surunkali va o'tkir yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bilan og'riqan bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir hodisalarini oldini olish uchun ishlatiladigan kolxitsinni ham o'rgangan.

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БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

8 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 8, НОМЕР 3

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